

Research and Innovation Action

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Abstract:

The SSHOC Project Management Plan is the main project management document and describes how major aspects of the project are managed, monitored and controlled. It is intended to provide guidance and direction for specific conduct, planning, and control activities such as schedule, efforts, internal communication, reporting procedures, adjustments, etc.

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Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D1.1 – Project Management Plan” of the Horizon2020 project “Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud” (hereinafter also referred to as “SSHOC”, project reference: 823782).

The SSHOC Project Management Plan is the central document describing major aspects of the project management process. It is intended to provide guidance and direction for specific management, planning, and control activities such as schedule, reporting, communication, quality, etc. The focus of this document is to describe the approaches being taken in the project to manage the various work packages, share and store documents, communicate among consortium members, control the quality of project deliverables, and provide links to other important procedures i.e. related to governance, described in Grant Agreement and/or Consortium Agreement.

The Project Management Plan is a living document and should be updated continuously throughout the project. Benefits of creating a Project Management Plan include:

- clearly define roles, responsibilities, processes and activities;
- increase probability that projects will be completed on-time, within budget, and with a high degree of quality;
- ensuring understanding of what was agreed upon;
- helping project teams identify and plan for how project activities will be managed (budget, quality, schedule, etc.).

The intended audience of the SSHOC Project Management Plan consists of members of the SSHOC consortium and the Project Officer at the controlling and granting side.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Coordinator
DoA	Description of Action
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures
FO	Financial Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
PMB	Project Management Board
PM	Person-Month
PO	Project Officer
PSB	Project Scientific Board
PMB	Project Management Board
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

Deliverable 1.1 details the Project Management Plan of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud - SSHOC project. The purpose of this document is to provide a documented plan for the management and control of the organizational, developmental and supporting processes necessary to the successful implementation of the project.

It outlines the goals and objectives and organizational structure; defines the responsibilities and roles of project participants; identifies the interactions among project partners; and specifies the general procedures and management tools that are implemented to ensure effective project management and successful project completion.

The document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement no. 823782 and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement.

The SSHOC project employs a standard project management approach based on documented timelines, regular communications, active follow up, and formal quality control and risk mitigation processes. To support its project management approach, the SSHOC project uses a cloud shared, revision history enabled and synced folders (provided by Google Drive service), Basecamp collaborative online platform and a set of dedicated conference calls. The combination of these solutions provides the team with facilities for sharing and managing documents, managing work package tasks, tracking progress against task deliverables, scheduling meetings and discussions, and generally ensuring that the distributed project team can proactively collaborate to meet project requirements.

In order to ensure that regular progress reports are produced on time by deliverable leaders, CESSDA ERIC as Coordinator, created procedures and templates. These procedures have been finalized to assure that actual resource consumption is tracked against plan, that any deviations from the plan are quickly surfaced and appropriate risk mitigation actions taken.

To facilitate on-going reporting activities and project team work, email lists have been created and conference calling facilities established. In addition, a project website has been developed to provide not only internal communications capabilities for the SSHOC team, but also to support the team's dissemination and exploitation activities.

Finally, formal quality control and risk management processes need to be established through Quality Assurance and Risk Assessment Plan (D1.2 due in August 2019) in order for the project outputs to meet the operational criteria and any deviations from initial plan are properly addressed.

2 Project objectives

The overall objective of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project is to realise the social sciences and humanities' part of European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Specifically, SSHOC aims at realising the transition from the current landscape with disciplinary silos and separated e-infrastructure facilities into a cloud-based infrastructure where data are FAIR, and tools and training are available for scholars from those domains in the social science and humanities that have adopted a data-driven scientific approach and that have an interest in the innovation and integration of their methodological frameworks.

SSHOC aims to realise the following specific objectives:

- Build the SSH Cloud - SSH Infrastructures are distributed with a number of limits for their re-use. A common SSH Cloud should provide a recognizable and accessible environment for data, tools & services, and training. SSHOC will develop a virtual infrastructure with existing and new infrastructures connected.
- Maximize re-use through Open Science and FAIR principles - The project will generate services for optimal re-use of data by making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR). It will also apply the FAIR principles to the creation of data as this will increase the efficiency and ease of creating and re-using new data.
- Interconnect existing and new infrastructures - The SSHOC ecosystem will use existing infrastructures already provided by the project partners and make existing tools and services better available. The project aims for synergies over disciplines and works towards a clustered cloud infrastructure making use of common elements, such as secured login, storage and computing power, and other e-infrastructures.
- Governance for SSH-EOSC - The SSHOC project will set up an appropriate governance model for the SSH part of the EOSC, considering the specificities of different sub-domains of the social sciences and humanities.

3 Project organisation

3.1 Consortium

The SSHOC consortium brings together all the key players in the European Social Sciences and Humanities needed to achieve the project aims of making data accessible across SSH subdomains and beyond, as well as to strengthen collaborations by development of joint standards, tools, procedures and processes. The consortium is formed of organisations from 16 European countries, covering all SSH ESFRI Landmarks and Projects, as well as important international SSH data infrastructures and associations. In total 45 partner organisations participate in the project: 20 beneficiaries and 25 Linked Third Parties.

3.2 Project organisational structure

The SSHOC organizational structure is contains the following Consortium Bodies, as defined in the Consortium Agreement:

- The SSHOC Scientific Board is the advisory and supervisory body of the consortium consisting of the heads of 5 participating ERICs (CESSDA, CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS, SHARE), ESFRI project (E-RIHS), and LIBER.
- The SSHOC Project Management Board is the key coordination and decision-making body for the execution of the Project relating to the provisions of the Grant Agreement, consisting of the work package leaders and a Coordinator representative.
- The Coordinator, CESSDA ERIC, represents the Project towards the EC as the Funding Authority and other third parties, acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority, bearing overall responsibility for the project implementation and coordination.

In terms of project management, the Project Management Board (PMB) is the central coordination body consisting of all WP leaders and the Coordinator representative, chairing the regular coordination meetings. PMB is ensuring the smooth performance of tasks against the Grant Agreement obligations. In addition, the

PMB should collect information related to progress of the project at least every 6 months, examine that information to assess the compliance of the project with the planned activities and, if necessary, propose modifications of the to the Scientific Board.

All Parties (Beneficiaries and Linked Third Parties) have responsibility to contribute to the wider management and decision making. Each Party can propose items for a PMB meeting. Proposals are submitted in a written form to the Coordinator. Each party has a veto right as described in Section 6.2.4. of the Consortium Agreement.

3.3 Roles and responsibilities

Each of the project partners have specific roles defined in the Grant Agreement and its Annexes. In general, all project partners should fulfil their tasks duly, timely and according to the distribution of work specified in Annex I or amended by the decisions of the Project Management Board or the Granting Authority. The timely delivery of all financial statements and reports to the Coordinator is of the highest priority.

The following project roles are defined:

a) Project Coordinator – individual representing the Coordinator (CESSDA ERIC)

- Responsible for overall project management and coordination of the decision-making process,
- Intermediary between the project partners and the EC,
- Monitors compliance of the partners with their obligations,
- Chairs the PMB meetings, proposes decisions and monitors the implementation of the project,
- Chairs the PSB meetings, participates decision making and reports on the project performance.

b) WP Leader

- Responsible for the overall coordination of the WP, supervision of the tasks, activities, milestones as well as the related deliverables,
- Prepares periodic reports for the PMB meetings,
- Reports to the Coordinator,
- Organizes communication within the respective WP and, together with the Project Coordinator and other WP Leaders, across WPs,
- Presenting the WP conclusions, decisions, results and deliverables at external meetings,
- Takes, in agreement with the Task Leaders, decisions at the WP level,
- Analyses and documents any Default of a party in relation to the own WP activities and preparing a respective proposal for an action plan to the Coordinator.

c) Task Leader

- Responsible for the timely implementation of the activities in the task and the reporting to the WP Leader,
- Takes, in agreement with the concerned WP Leader, decisions at the task level.

d) Team member

- Has particular skills that are required to complete project tasks,

- Successfully performs the allocated tasks, keeping the Task leader informed of progress as well as any issues that may arise.

3.1.1 List of WP and Task leaders

The SSHOC project consist of 10 work packages with 43 separate tasks led by partners from 13 partnering institutions across Europe. The comprehensive list of Work Packages, tasks and leading institutions is provided below in Table 1.

TABLE 1: LIST OF WP AND TASK LEADING INSTITUTIONS

WP / Task	Organisation
WP1 Project Management and Administration	CESSDA
1.1 Administrative Project Management	CESSDA
1.2 Quality Assurance & Risk Assessment	CESSDA
1.3 Project Reporting	CESSDA
WP2 Communication and Dissemination	TRUST-IT
2.1 Communication Strategy	CESSDA-AUSSDA
2.2 Within-Cluster Communication	TRUST-IT
2.3 Task 2.3 SSHOC EOSC Gateway	TRUST-IT
WP3 Lifting Tools to the Cloud	CLARIN
3.1 Multilingual Terminology	CNR
3.2 Selected Ontologies and Vocabularies	CLARIN
3.3 Text & Data Mining	CLARIN
3.4 Making Data FINDable by being Citable	DARIAH/CNRS (Huma-Num)
3.5 Data and Metadata Interoperability Hub	CESSDA FSD
3.6 Making Data Re-usable (actionable)	CLARIN/KNAW
WP4 Innovations in Data Production	ESS
4.1 A sample management system for cross-national web surveys	ESS - City
4.2 Preparing SSH tools for Computer Assisted Translation	ESS- UPF & SHARE-MEA
4.3 Applying Computer Assisted Translation in Social Surveys	ESS-UPF
4.4 Voice recorded interviews and audio analysis	KNAW (GGP)
4.5 Social policy APIs for social surveys	KNAW (GGP)
4.6 Semantic annotation of Heritage Science Data	CNRS (ERIHS)
4.7 Modeling the SSHOC data life cycle	FORTH (ERIHS)
WP5 Innovations in data access	SHARE-ERIC
5.1 Legal, ethical and technical issues of access to Biomedical data	SHARE-ERIC
5.2 Hosting and sharing data repositories	KNAW (DANS)
5.3 Legal and Ethical Issues	CESSDA-NSD
5.4 Remote Access to Sensitive Data	CESSDA-GESIS
5.5 Preparing cross-national survey data for the EOSC. ESS pilot/use case	ESS-NSD
5.6 Issues in providing Open Data in Heritage Science and Archaeology	E-RIHS (UCL/ADS) & E-RIHS (UCL/NG)
5.7 LOD archaeology case study	E-RIHS (DAI)

WP6 Fostering Communities & Building Expertise	LIBER
6.1 Mapping the Landscape and Developing Strategies to Foster Communities, Empower Users, and Build Expertise	LIBER
6.2 Fostering Communities: Engaging New & Existing Users	CESSDA-ADP
6.3 Empowering Users: Training Materials and Learning Paths	DARIAH-OEAW
6.4 Building Expertise: the SSHOC Training Network	KNAW (DANS)
6.5 Coordinating Targeted Training in the Social Sciences and Humanities	CLARIN-UL-FF
WP7 Creating the SSH Open Marketplace	DARIAH
7.1 User Requirements, Conceptual Model and System Architecture of the SSH Open Marketplace	DARIAH-SUB
7.2 Development of the Marketplace Application	DARIAH-OEAW
7.3 Marketplace Interoperability	CLARIN
7.4 Governance: Population, Curation & Sustainability of the Marketplace	DARIAH/CNRS (Huma-Num)
WP8 Governance/Sustainability/Quality Assurance	CNR
8.1 Governance & Sustainability	CLARIN
8.2 Trust & Quality Assurance	CESSDA-FSD
8.3 Legal and Ethical Issues	CESSDA-NSD
8.4 Overarching Clusters (Ari Asmi)	CNR
WP9 Data Communities	UNOTT
9.1 Identifying shared and unique challenges for SSH data communities; Evaluation and Usability Report	UNOTT
9.2 Ethnic and Migration Studies	SciencesPo
9.3 Electoral Studies	UNOTT
9.4 Heritage Science and Humanities	CNR

4 Project timeline

SSHOC project has a planned duration of 40 months. It has started on 1 January 2019, and planned finalisation of the project is on 30 April 2022. The main activities should be fulfilled in 3 years' time, however, additional 4 months were added to accommodate any possible delays within the project duration that could occur due to lengthy processes of hiring additional project-based associates in the beginning of the project or adjustments connected to replacement of staff due to expected/usual rates of staff mobility at partnering institutions.

Project activities are based on deliverables and milestones. In total there are 101 deliverables defined, high majority in the form of public reports. The production timeline for deliverables before the set deadlines is planned in the following manner:

- 4 weeks before the deadline: drafting, writing and completing should be done by the partner responsible for deliverable in coordination with the task and WP leader. The Word version should be created and shared via Google Drive.
- 3 weeks before: the internal review should commence. Reviewers should be selected in advance and informed via mailing list to start the review.
- 2 weeks before: final and reviewed draft should be sent to the Coordinator for the final review and editing.
- Deadline: the .pdf version of the deliverable is generated and uploaded to the Participant Portal designated space by the Coordinator.

FIGURE 1: MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES TIMELINE

There are several specific requirements connected to the review and publication of the deliverables. At least one reviewer per deliverable should be available, but more can be chosen if needed or suitable. The peer reviewer should be chosen from an organisation other than the one(s) responsible for the deliverable. The approval delegate for each deliverable is usually the WP leader.

Publication of deliverable should be done via SSHOC website, once the deliverable has been approved by the EC.

Any delays of deliverables should be communicated in advance with the WP leader and Coordinator, and plausible explanations should be offered to EC with the upload of the final version.

5 Project resources

The maximum EU contribution (and the maximum grant amount) approved for the SSHOC project is €14,455,594.08, at the reimbursement rate of 100%. The deducted guarantee fund of 5% is €722,779.70. The pre-financing amount allocated to the consortium in the beginning of the project duration is €7,709,650.18. The budget is distributed among 20 beneficiaries and 25 Linked Third Parties (overview of exact allocations per partner is shown in Table 2 below).

TABLE 2: BUDGET PER PARTNER

No.	Abbreviation	A) Total grant	B) Guarantee fund 5%	C)Pre- financing 53,33%	D) 1 st instalment (C-D)
1	CESSDA ERIC	€419,375.00	€20,968.75	€223,652.69	€202,683.94
1.1	NSD	€285,750.00	€14,287.50	€152,390.48	€138,102.98
1.2	UKDS	€276,231.25	€13,811.56	€147,314.13	€133,502.56
1.3	UL-ADP	€85,062.50	€4,253.13	€45,363.83	€41,110.71
1.4	GESIS	€288,100.00	€14,405.00	€153,643.73	€139,238.73
1.5	SND	€155,000.00	€7,750.00	€82,661.50	€74,911.50
1.6	UTA-FSD	€228,662.50	€11,433.13	€121,945.71	€110,512.59
1.7	FORS	€113,750.00	€5,687.50	€60,662.88	€54,975.38
1.8	DNA	€74,133.13	€3,706.66	€39,535.20	€35,828.54
1.9	AUSSDA	€150,000.00	€7,500.00	€79,995.00	€72,495.00
2	ESS ERIC	€50,000.00	€2,500.00	€26,665.00	€24,165.00
2.1	City	€257,991.88	€12,899.59	€137,587.07	€124,687.47
2.2	GESIS	€140,175.00	€7,008.75	€74,755.33	€67,746.58
2.3	UPF	€331,250.00	€16,562.50	€176,655.63	€160,093.13
2.4	NSD	€576,750.00	€28,837.50	€307,580.78	€278,743.28
3	SHARE ERIC	€0.00	€0.00	€0.00	€0.00
3.1	MPISOC	€768,359.38	€38,417.97	€409,766.05	€371,348.09
3.2	UniVe	€212,850.00	€10,642.50	€113,512.91	€102,870.41
4	CLARIN ERIC	€1,139,062.50	€56,953.13	€607,462.03	€550,508.91
4.1	Athena	€139,375.00	€6,968.75	€74,328.69	€67,359.94
4.2	EKUT	€249,625.00	€12,481.25	€133,125.01	€120,643.76
4.3	CUNI	€183,687.50	€9,184.38	€97,960.54	€88,776.17
4.4	UL-FF	€143,312.50	€7,165.63	€76,428.56	€69,262.93
4.5	RUN	€173,125.00	€8,656.25	€92,327.56	€83,671.31
5	DARIAH ERIC	€182,812.50	€9,140.63	€97,493.91	€88,353.28
5.1	PSNC	€411,250.00	€20,562.50	€219,319.63	€198,757.13
5.2	OEAW	€477,250.00	€23,862.50	€254,517.43	€230,654.93
5.3	UGOE	€601,562.50	€30,078.13	€320,813.28	€290,735.16
6	LIBER	€450,937.50	€22,546.88	€240,484.97	€217,938.09
7	KNAW – GGP	€783,781.25	€39,189.06	€417,990.54	€378,801.48
8	UoY – ADS	€93,981.25	€4,699.06	€50,120.20	€45,421.14

9	TiU	€279,218.75	€13,960.94	€148,907.36	€134,946.42
10	TRUST-IT	€259,062.50	€12,953.13	€138,158.03	€125,204.91
10.1	Trust-SRL	€154,062.50	€7,703.13	€82,161.53	€74,458.41
10.2	COMMpla	€74,218.75	€3,710.94	€39,580.86	€35,869.92
11	SWC	€241,812.50	€12,090.63	€128,958.61	€116,867.98
12	SCIENCES PO	€755,280.00	€37,764.00	€402,790.82	€365,026.82
13	UNOTT	€227,031.25	€11,351.56	€121,075.77	€109,724.20
14	DAI	€146,787.50	€7,339.38	€78,281.77	€70,942.40
15	CNRS	€587,187.50	€29,359.38	€313,147.09	€283,787.72
16	CNR	€880,515.00	€44,025.75	€469,578.65	€425,552.90
17	UCL	€99,632.19	€4,981.61	€53,133.85	€48,152.24
18	FORTH	€146,250.00	€7,312.50	€77,995.13	€70,682.63
19	CentERdata	€1,050,055.00	€52,502.75	€559,994.33	€507,491.58
20	NG	€111,277.50	€5,563.88	€59,310.91	€53,747.03

The project was initially formed of nine work packages, with leadership assigned according to expertise of the core partners in the SSHOC proposal. Work Package 1 is led by CESSDA ERIC, the Coordinator. Work Package 2 is led by TRUST-IT, one of several SMEs in the project. Work Packages 3-5, and 7 are led by ESFRI Landmarks: CLARIN ERIC, ESS ERIC, SHARE ERIC, and DARIAH ERIC. Work Package 6 is led by LIBER, the European Association of Research Libraries. Work Package 8 is led by CNR as part of the ESFRI project E-RIHS. Finally, Work Package 9 is led by the University of Nottingham-Election studies. Work Package 10 on Ethical Issues was added in the post award phase by the EC and is led by the Coordinator.

CESSDA ERIC, as the Coordinator, and all participating ESFRI Landmarks and projects, have deployed substantial efforts in order to ensure the best possible management of the project, and delivery of the project outputs. In total, 1,754.50 person-months were planned to fulfil all consortium obligations. The overview of each partner's engagement in the SSHOC project is given in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3: EFFORTS (IN PM) PER WP AND PARTNER

No.	Abbreviation	WP1 PM	WP2 PM	WP3 PM	WP4 PM	WP5 PM	WP6 PM	WP7 PM	WP8 PM	WP9 PM	Total PM
1	CESSDA ERIC	36.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	2.0	0.0	42.0
1.1	NSD	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.0	4.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	26.5
1.2	UKDS	0.5	0.0	8.0	0.0	4.0	6.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	24.5
1.3	UL-ADP	0.5	1.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	15.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.5
1.4	GESIS	0.5	0.0	4.0	0.0	18.0	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	30.5
1.5	SND	0.5	0.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	14.5
1.6	UTA-FSD	0.5	0.0	14.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.0	0.0	24.5
1.7	FORS	0.5	0.0	4.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.5
1.8	DNA	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.5
1.9	AUSSDA	0.5	10.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	18.5
2	ESS ERIC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
2.1	City	2.5	0.0	0.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	28.5
2.2	GESIS	0.5	0.0	0.0	11.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.5
2.3	UPF	0.5	0.0	0.0	47.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	48.0
2.4	NSD	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	53.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	53.5
3	SHARE ERIC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3.1	MPISOC	4.5	0.0	0.0	36.0	71.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	112.5
3.2	UniVe	0.0	0.0	36.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.0
4	CLARIN ERIC	3.0	2.0	69.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	15.0	14.0	0.0	119.0
4.1	Athena	0.5	0.0	18.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	20.5
4.2	EKUT	0.5	0.0	25.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.5
4.3	CUNI	0.5	0.0	12.0	16.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.5

4.4	UL-FF	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	30.5
4.5	RUN	0.5	0.0	0.0	12.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.5
5	DARIAH ERIC	2.5	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	12.0	4.0	0.0	25.5
5.1	PSNC	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.0	0.0	42.0	6.0	0.0	63.5
5.2	OEAW	0.5	0.0	12.0	0.0	0.0	15.0	44.0	0.0	0.0	71.5
5.3	UGOE	0.5	0.0	31.0	0.0	10.0	0.0	31.0	0.0	0.0	72.5
6	LIBER	2.5	8.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	23.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	41.5
7	KNAW	1.0	0.0	3.0	36.0	18.0	7.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	71.0
8	UoY - ADS	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.0
9	TiU	0.5	0.0	11.0	13.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.5
10	TRUST-IT	1.0	18.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2	2.0	0.8	0.0	25.0
10.1	Trust-SRL	1.0	18.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2	2.0	0.8	0.0	25.0
10.2	COMMpla	0.5	9.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.6	1.0	0.4	0.0	12.5
11	SWC	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.0	0.0	14.0	30.5
12	SCIENCES PO	0.5	0.0	0.0	71.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.0	107.5
13	UNOTT	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.0	10.5
14	DAI	0.5	0.0	4.0	4.0	10.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.0
15	CNRS	1.0	4.0	20.0	16.0	0.0	6.0	32.0	0.0	4.0	83.0
16	CNR	2.5	5.0	38.0	23.0	26.0	6.0	8.0	23.0	22.0	153.5
17	UCL	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.5
18	FORTH	0.5	0.0	4.0	14.5	0.0	0.0	4.0	0.0	0.0	23.0
19	CentERdata	0.5	0.0	36.0	56.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	116.5
20	National Gallery	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.0
	TOTALS	73.0	78.0	367.0	388.0	314.5	139.0	215.0	84.0	96.0	1,754.5

5.1 Adjustments

Any adjustments in terms of allocated budget, activities or staff efforts, should be communicated with the Project Officer (PO). Minor adjustments, including budget transfers up to 20% of the total eligible costs of a given beneficiary, do not require prior approval of the Granting authority. Such adjustments will be communicated with the Coordinator and all involved parties and reported within the periodic and/or final reporting process.

However, major adjustments, if needed, should be addressed through an amendment procedure described in Art. II.13 of the Grant Agreement. Amendments are used in order to modify the grant agreement and its annexes and could be requested at any time during the lifetime of the project, but at the latest 30 days before the closing date of the action.

6 Project coordination related communication

6.1 Internal communication

The SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (outlined in D2.1) sets the communications framework for this project. It serves as a guide for communications throughout the life of the project and will be updated as required. This plan identifies and defines the goals and channels of communication, especially towards external stakeholders and SSHOC communities.

For the purpose of the project coordination and reporting purposes, the Project management plan further details the internal communication tools and procedures.

Since its start in January 2019, the SSHOC project has relied on a collaboration tool suite that supports the organization and management of the project in an easy manner and has made the communication among the partners most efficient. It comprises of a number of dedicated mailing lists, a Basecamp collaboration platform as well as cloud-based storage solution for the collaborative creation, management and versioning of documents.

6.1.1 *Contact list*

A project team directory is represented in a form of a Google sheet stored in the Implementation folder within the SSHOC Document repository. In the later phase of the project, a more advanced tool may be used if required. Project beneficiaries should keep the team directory regularly updated. Access rights and roles within the project are set based on the information provided in the team directory.

6.1.2 *Electronic mails and mailing lists*

Several target group-specific mailing lists have been established to address SSHOC-relevant topics and activities as well as circulate important SSHOC-related news among the project members. A general mailing list (consortium @sshopencloud.eu) with currently around 200 subscribers is used for internal communication.

6.1.3 *Conference calls*

A regular PMB coordination calls are organized by the Coordinator and its team (CO) every 2 weeks. The CO drafts and publishes the agenda within the rolling minutes documented. Participants are invited to participate in creation of the agenda and add items of interest and importance to PMB. WP leaders are expected to participate in these calls in an active and reliable manner. If anyone is unable to be present, the notice should be given in advance and feedback provided concerning relevant points in the agenda.

Moreover, telephone and online conferences are scheduled on a regular basis for individual Work Packages. These calls should also be announced in the SSHOC calendar on Basecamp.

Tools mostly used for these calls are Skype and GoToMeeting.

6.1.4 Meetings

The consortium meetings are planned twice a year providing the discussion platform where all project partners can meet and discuss ongoing work, outputs and next steps to be taken. Each meeting should be organized by another core partner responsible for venue, agenda, co-located events, like community meetups with stakeholders, and invitation of external guests. Focus of these meetings is mainly on the following aspects:

- Plenary sessions to summarize the project's outputs and lessons learned; definition of actions and measures to meet the project's objectives; progress reporting and review preparations.
- WP related sessions to define WP related actions, issues and contingency measures.

The partners should also meet in different subgroups cross WP task forces to plan and discuss specific parts of work and collaboration efforts with respect to their WPs and tasks.

6.2 Document repository

Location: <https://drive.google.com/>

Google Drive (and Google Team Drive as alternative) is agreed and used as a project document repository and basis for project management, administration and collaboration. It contains all important information needed for ongoing work and collaboration across WPs. All project partners have access to all information stored in Google Drive SSHOC folders.

Research or sensitive data should be managed following the specific legal regulative and established best practices at the organisations responsible for the collection and processing of sensitive data. Storing of such data on Google Drive should be avoided. The basic structure of the document repository for the SSHOC project is shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 2:SSHOC DOCUMENT REPOSITORY STRUCTURE

6.3 Online collaboration platform

Location: <https://3.basecamp.com/4165192/>

Basecamp 3 will be used as a collaboration platform during the SSHOC project implementation. Basecamp is one of the most popular online project management suites available. It has a short learning time and majority of SSHOC team members have previous experience with the tool.

The basic structure used for SSHOC includes the following collaboration spaces:

- Consortium – Project-wide communication, all project contacts are included by default,
- Work Packages – each WP has a separate collaboration space, WP members are involved by default, observers can join by contacting the WP Leader in charge or PM
- Teams – specific thematic, ad-hoc or permanent teams, initiative to form the teams comes from the team members

Each collaboration space has the following Basecamp functionalities available:

- To-Dos – for tracking tasks and assigning priorities
- Message Board – for sharing announcements, updates and key communication; instant forwarders or daily reports sent by e-mail
- Campfire – for casual chat and quick discussions
- Pings – for direct or private communication between project members
- Schedule – for tracking progress, deadlines and milestones; publishing the important dates or events
- Docs & Files – for storing and organising documents into folders; allows versioning

FIGURE 3: BASECAMP WELCOME SCREEN AND WP COLLABORATION SPACE

7 Project reporting

The project reporting will include internal reports (each 6 months) and official Technical reports to the EC due in Month 18 and month 36, and the final report due in Month 40.

The SSHOC Coordination team will have up to 60 days after the reporting period has ended to upload all the relevant documents onto the EC portal. WP leaders and financial contacts for each party will upload their materials onto the Project Document Repository no later than one month after the end of the reporting period.

Technical reports comprising activities' progress will be sent to the PMB for approval. PMB is expected to respond in the following two weeks. The Coordination team will have additional two weeks to assemble the reports and submit them to the EC, and four weeks to assemble the financial reports (not reviewed by PMB).

7.1 Internal monitoring

The project-internal monitoring process will include regular 6-monthly feedback on budget spending from all project partners. The purpose of internal reporting is to provide feedback and sense of direction in usage of allocated Person-Months and related budget spent. Costs' control will serve as basis for identification and analysis of possible deviations, adjustments of planning and contingency measures, if necessary.

Special attention is devoted to production of a separate Certificate on the financial statements (CFS) for each beneficiary and Linked Third Party exceeding a total contribution of €325.000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices. Details on procedure for sending the CFS to the EC is described in Grant Agreement (Article 20.4).

Specific template for internal reporting is provided in the document repository.

Specific guidelines (wiki) for all management related topics will be in place before the first internal reporting deadline and, if necessary, will be adjusted afterwards.

8 References

- SSHOC Grant Agreement
- SSHOC Consortium Agreement
- SSHOC Overall Communication and Outreach Plan (D2.1)
- H2020 Online Manual
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management_en.htm

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